

INTERCULTURAL TEACHING STRATEGIES IN ENGLISH LESSONS

Khazratova Gulchekhra Sharipovna
senior teacher, Tashkent Medical Academy

Annotation. Intercultural competence (IC) as an essential part of conceptualization of the cultural dimension in FLT has been promoted by educationalists as the most preferred type of competence. One of the challenges of incorporating IC into FLT is to move from the recognition of IC as a model of teaching (Byram, Nichols and Stevens, 2001) to the development of practical applications. This can be due to the fact that teachers do not have sufficient knowledge of the theory behind the concept and consequently, have difficulties to implement the curriculum requirements with regards to IC into their teaching. The purpose of this study was to investigate how teachers of English in upper secondary schools in Sweden interpret the concept of IC and, accordingly, what is their view of culture in English language teaching. In order to answer the research question, I used an exploratory investigation by adopting a qualitative research method in form of semi-structured interviews.

Key words. Intercultural competence, culture, English Language Teaching, Byram's savoirs, teacher cognition.

Аннотация. Межкультурная компетентность (МК) как неотъемлемая часть концептуализации культурного измерения в FLT была пропагандирована педагогами как наиболее предпочтительный тип компетентности. Одной из проблем включения МК в FLT является переход от признания ИК в качестве модели обучения (Байрам, Николс и Стивенс, 2001) к разработке практических приложений. Это может быть связано с тем, что учителя не обладают достаточными знаниями теории, лежащей в основе

этой концепции, и, следовательно, испытывают трудности с внедрением требований учебной программы в отношении ИК в свое обучение. Целью данного исследования было выяснить, как преподаватели английского языка в старших классах средней школы Швеции интерпретируют концепцию ИС и, соответственно, каков их взгляд на культуру преподавания английского языка. Чтобы ответить на вопрос исследования, я использовал предварительное исследование, применив качественный метод исследования в форме полуструктурированных интервью.

Ключевые слова. Межкультурная компетентность, культура, преподавание английского языка, знания Байрама, познание учителя.

Research on teaching in other subjects has revealed some effective strategies for raising students' interest in school-based learning. One of them is supporting students' self-determination during lessons, that is, promoting their feelings of autonomy, competence, and social relatedness in class.

Different developments in our society had an impact on language teaching strategies and attitudes towards foreign language learning. As a response to the acknowledgement of social and cultural significance in language teaching, a revolutionary concept of intercultural competence (IC) emerged over the last two decades. Research that have followed the emergence of this conception contributed to the development of a theoretical framework and practical applications for IC. The purpose of developing IC in all fields of education, and particularly in FLT is to increase international and cross-cultural acceptance and tolerance among learners. Teaching IC does not only entail acquainting learners with knowledge about different cultures, but also with a set of practices that necessitate knowledge, skills and attitudes, including critical cultural awareness, which teachers should incorporate in their classroom practice by advocating cultural and linguistic relativity. The intercultural element in the FLT has become of a great concern not only for linguists or policy makers but also for teachers. Currently, the field of FLT encounters the inevitable process of globalization and technological expansion

which is also reflected in the development of foreign language curricula around the world. Naturally, the curriculum for upper secondary schools in Sweden follows the contemporary trend in language teaching methodology and includes the significance of culture and IC in teaching English. It states that: “Students should be given the opportunity to develop knowledge of living conditions, social issues and cultural features in different contexts and parts of the world where English is used. Teaching should encourage students' curiosity in language and culture, and give them the opportunity to develop plurilingualism where skills in different languages interact and support each other.” (Skolverket, 2012a, p. 1).

The importance of developing IC in parallel with communicative competence supported by numerous studies and reflected in the policy documents has caused one of the greatest pedagogical challenges. Also, the question of how the English language teachers perceive language and culture teaching, interculturality, and their role as culture teachers have been posed by a number of researchers (Paige et al., 2003). The purpose of this study is to focus specifically on English teachers' perception of the concept of IC and on how this perception is reflected in the description of their teaching practice. To answer this question, six English teachers for upper secondary school in Sweden will be interviewed in order to, firstly, investigate their understanding of IC and explore what features of their teaching practice relate to the theoretical framework of IC, and secondly, conclude what are the obstacles and the opportunities for teaching IC in the existing situation based on the teachers' responses.

The overview of the development of teaching methods and objectives clearly illustrates that teaching language and culture has not always been integrated and pedagogically justified. Over the years, the FLT profession had been determined by emergence of teaching methods that increased and declined in popularity. Practical applications of theoretical findings in the field of ELT include a wide variety of methods such as: The Classical Method, The Grammar Translation Method, The Direct Method, and Audiolingual Method, which regard a language

as a system of hierarchically arranged, rule-governed structures (Brown, 2007). In the late 1950's Noam Chomsky established a number of objectives and language theories that have been applied and developed in language teaching practice. Those objectives highlighted the study of language as a system independent from any particular context (Cetinavci, 2012). In his study Chomsky argues against the sterility of behaviorism and claims that the nature of language and process of language acquisition can only be explained in terms of genetically transmitted language faculty (Pütz, 1992). This rejection of behaviorism in language learning contributed to rejection of the Audiolingual Method and implementation of so called Cognitive Code Learning in ELT (Brown, 2007). In the 1970's, representing a major change of emphasis, presents the concept of Communicative Competence (CC) which arises mainly as a conjunction of two independent developments: that of Chomsky's transformational generative grammar, on the one hand, and the ethnography of communication, on the other (Hymes, 1992).

As knowledge of culture provides a crucial base of knowledge of a language, it is very often rooted in a national conception of culture and language. This has been very problematic given that English is now used as a global lingua franca and has no specific geographical boundaries (Baker, 2011). There are many studies that criticize teaching English with a most exclusive focus on native varieties and their cultures. Decke-Cornill (2003) and Mauranen and Ranta (2009) point out that English should be taught as a lingua franca, where there is a break of a traditional assumption that language associated with one or more specific cultures. However, as Decke-Cornill's study suggest, many teachers, especially those with strong academic qualifications rely heavily on an emphasis on specific countries and cultures. Correspondingly, Tornberg (2000) points out that despite a requisite to give culture dimension in FLT a heavier emphasis, the concept of culture is not being reviewed. This results in culture being associated mostly with nationality in foreign language curricula. Culture, however, irrespective of its affiliation has also an aspect of fluidity. Tornberg (2000), has developed three different analytical

perspectives on communication and culture: culture as a fact fulfilled – it implies a conception of culture as nationally defined; a future competence – expresses that there is an individual behavioral skill to be developed; and third, culture as an encounter in an open landscape. While the first two recognize culture in foreign language teaching and learning as a product, the third one, based on Kramsch concept of a third place sees culture as a process that emphasizes the student's influential role, self-analysis, and responsibility for participation in the real-time experience.

In order to address the research question, I used an exploratory investigation by adopting a qualitative research method in form of semi-structured interviews. The participants in this research are six English teachers of different upper secondary schools in Sweden, from which five teach English at upper secondary and one at upper secondary for adults. This exploratory research aims to focus on participants' beliefs, understanding and perception as this is on the subject of this study and a methodology in form of interviews is an effective tool to achieve this purpose. Besides, a semi-structured interview was the most suitable type of interview for this study because it allows an interviewer to follow up interesting developments and let the interviewee elaborate on certain issues. It also allows to ask the interviewee the same questions but not necessarily in the same order or wording, which was necessary in this research since some of the participants touched upon various aspects while answering particular questions. My goals, as an interviewer, were: to let the interview flow naturally by seamlessly connecting subsequent questions, trying to be neutral and not imposing any personal bias, and let the interviewee dictate the pace focusing primarily on listening. This emic approach helped to obtain information about the participants' understanding of the investigated topic and allowed developing of different themes, patterns and ideas. Interviews are also suitable tools of phenomenographic methodology in qualitative research that provide different ways in which people think of various concepts and

aims to discover qualitatively different ways of how people experience, understand and interpret various aspects of an investigated phenomena (Marton, 1986).

The study has revealed a number of deficiencies in the teachers' understanding of IC. Consequently, these deficiencies create obstacles for the teachers to effectively promote interculturality in their teaching practice. The results show that there are opportunities for improvement and therefore several implementations for teaching. First of all, culture teaching requires a critical dimension. Therefore, teachers and teacher students need deeper knowledge of the cultural aspect in FLT that should be anchored in the available theories and frameworks. Secondly, policy documents should include a clear and applicable definition of IC and should clarify the assessment criteria. At the moment, the concept of IC is being left for individual interpretation by a teacher who applies this interpretation into his/her classroom practice. For that reason, teachers should be familiarized with the recent research with regards to IC and encouraged to problematize the curriculum content with regards to culture teaching.

References

1. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching*. Fifth Edition. NY: Pearson Education, Inc.
2. Decke-Cornill, H. (2003). "We would have to invent the language we are supposed to teach". *The issue of English as a Lingua Franca in Germany*. In Byram, M., & Grundy, P. (eds) *Context and culture in language teaching and learning*. Clevedon: Multilingual Matters, pp. 59-71.
3. Hymes, D.H. (1992). *The concept of communicative competence revisited*. In Pütz, M. (1992). *Thirty years of linguistic evolution: Studies in honour of René Dirven on the occasion of his sixtieth birthday*. Philadelphia: J. Benjamins Pub.

4. Mauranen, A., & Ranta, E. (2009). English as a Lingua Franca: Studies and Findings. Cambridge Scholars Publishing
5. Marton, F. (1986). Phenomenography - A research approach investigating different understandings of reality. *Journal of Thought*, 21, 28-49.
6. Skolverket (2012b). Kommentarmaterial till kursplanen i engelska. Stockholm: Skolverket.
7. Tornberg, U. (2000). Om språkundervisning i mellanrummet – och talet om ”kultur” och ”kommunikation” i kursplaner och läromedel från 1962 till 2000. *Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis*.
8. Tashpulatova, D., & Siddiqova, I. (2021, April). A CRITIQUE OF THE VIEW OF ANTONYMY AS A RELATION BETWEEN WORD FORMS. In *Конференции*.
9. qizi Turaboyeva, S. Z., & qizi Tashpulatova, D. X. (2022). O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDAGI AXLOQIY QADRIYATLAR MAZMUNINI IFODALOVCHI BIRLIKLARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(1), 143-147.
10. Тошпулатова, Д. Х. (2019). ПОНЯТИЕ И ВИДЫ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННОМУ ЯЗЫКУ. АНАЛИЗ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ КОНЦЕПЦИЙ. *Вопросы педагогики*, (7-2), 118-121.
11. ТАШПУЛАТОВА, Д. PRAGMATIC APHORISMS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FEATURE AND THE PRINCIPLES OF THEIR TRANSMISSION IN THE CORPUS. *СООТНОШЕНИЕ ПАРАЛИНГВИСТИКИ И РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В РАЗНЫХ ЛИНГВОКУЛЬТУРАХ*.